

An Empirical Exploration on Mindfulness and Mindful Consumption

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Abstract: *Mindfulness is a very active research topic and is closely related to consumption behavioral aspects and attitudes. On the other hand, the concept of mindful consumption is a rather new emerging field in consumer behavior literature with a few studies addressing the key elements. It focuses mainly on the selection of what we are buying with intended consciousness and attention and enables us to discern the bare benefits from a promoted product and to make conscious choices that are in accordance with our values and have positive effects to ourselves, the society and nature. This study aims to explore some key dimensions of mindfulness and mindful consumption area and present the initial empirical findings from a survey held among Greek consumers. It is promising to see that the respondents in their majority are conscious about not being mindful at the time being, but at the same time they are willing to cultivate mindfulness. This will have a positive impact towards higher levels of mindful consumption. Results are of importance for social scientists and marketing research and can be further elaborated in subsequent research.*

Keywords: Mindfulness, Mindful consumption

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, the topic of mindfulness is being encountered in increasing journal publications. Academic publications related to mindfulness, in 2020, are almost ten times the publications of 2010 and studies related to mindfulness are widely applied to many fields: psychology, medicine, education etc. (Kabat-Zinn and Williams, 2011). In parallel, many organizations including Google company, USA army, athletic teams and educational institutes, among others, adopt mindfulness practices in order to improve their performance (Confino, 2014; Bahl et al, 2016). At the same time, websites, web applications, social media accounts and books offer a diverse mix of media that spread the notion of mindfulness in multiple aspects of people's lives. Mobile applications is a very effective way of integrating mindfulness into everybody's daily lives, as they have rich material and useful tools to keep the user alert. According to web statistics, mindfulness and meditation mobile application are increasing globally despite the challenges (TechCrunch, 2020). Given the relationship of mindfulness to consumption, it is likely that the increasing trend will continue in the next years.

Another emerging trend in academic literature is the concept of mindful consumption, which is considered as an answer to mindless, automated consumption and overconsumption. It is defined as the selection of what we are buying with intended consciousness and attention (Sheth et al. 2011). This, in turn, enables us to discern the bare benefit from a promoted product and to choose products according to our values that are beneficial for ourselves, the society and the environment. Although few research has been conducted referring to this concept, literature indicates that there is positive relationship between mindfulness, sustainable consumption, and certain intrinsic values.

Within the above context, this work aims to contribute in the current mindfulness research stream and provide some useful insights on the relationship between mindfulness and consumption. Specifically, it explores the relationship

between mindfulness, sustainable consumption and specific intrinsic values, that according to the literature seem to be related, however field studies are relatively limited. To achieve this, a field survey was performed on a sample of Greek adult consumers, from a mindfulness aware population. According to relevant research, sustainable consumption behaviors were measured by the assessment of three related behaviors: environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, preference for companies with perceived Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and downshifting consumption. For the assessment of each of the above three categories (constructs), items of scales widely used at similar academic research were utilized.

The most important conclusion emerging from the specific study is that there seems to be a positive correlation between mindfulness, sustainable consumption, and specific intrinsic values, even if correlations were moderate or low. This however, can be attributed to the limitations of the specific survey.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Initially, an introduction to the concepts of mindfulness and mindful consumption is presented and review of relevant research in the domain. Next, the survey is introduced and the key findings are presented. Finally, there is discussion on the key outcomes and contributions of this work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mindfulness

The word “mindfulness” originates from the Pali language word “sati”, which means “to remember”. However, since mindfulness is considered as a form of consciousness, it means “presence of mind” (Bodhi, 2000). It is based on attention to and awareness of what is happening here and now (Brown & Ryan, 2003). It is defined as the unbiased awareness that derives from the intended attention to what is happening at the present moment, treated with open mind, acceptance and empathy (Stanszus, 2017). “What is happening” does not only mean the events around us or our actions, but also our thoughts, our feelings and the behavioral patterns we may recognize (Rosenberg, 2004); or in other words, the interpretation that we give onto the facts occurring in our environment (Hayes et al., 2006). Such behavioral patterns are, among others, the consumption patterns, adopted unintentionally overtime (Rosenberg, 2004).

There is a stream of thought which claims that mindfulness, as inherent and conscious attention and awareness, can be cultivated (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Kabat-Zinn, 2003). However, the intensity of mindfulness, the willingness to cultivate it and the efficiency of implementing it, differs among people (depending on one’s inclination and discipline) and throughout one’s life. The cultivation of mindfulness can be achieved either by mindfulness meditation (Kabat-Zinn, 1982), or by intentional awareness of the present external stimuli (Langer & Moldoveanu, 2000). The fact that mindfulness can be cultivated, along with the findings that it offers many positive effects to well-being, has encouraged many implications of mindfulness in medicine and other disciplines. However, there is no consensus among researchers on the factors, and mainly in the demographics like age and gender, that affect it. Until today, there are a very few studies about which demographic factors affect mindfulness and they only focus on age and gender (Mogilner et al., 2011; Shook et al, 2017; Alispahic & Hasanbegovic-Anic, 2017).

Another, interesting aspect is that there is some commercial perspective in the mindfulness concept. According to Langer and Moldoveanu (2000), we need to be aware of anything new that emerges in our perspective, regardless its importance. For example, we need to be aware during our weekly visit at the supermarket that may be considered as an unimportant, routine activity and can easily be treated without consciousness and lead to mindless purchases. In a commercial point of view, as Pollock et al. (1998) have shown, mindfulness can reduce the vulnerability to the influence of marketing techniques on consumers.

Mindful consumption

Sheth et al. (2011) support that the act of consumption consists of two parts:

a) The mentality which consists of the values and attitudes that have to do with consumption. This is crucial because on one hand it defines consumption behavior and on the other hand it affects the way we interpret our consumption choices and consequently our future consumption behavior.

b) The consumption choices or consumption behavior.

The above distinction means that, for a more conscious consumption behavior, free from mindless consumption patterns, both mentality and consumption behavior should change. For the mentality, the vehicle of such a change is considering and focusing on the consequences of consumption. As far as behavior is concerned, the adoption of

moderate consumption habits (or in other words, the mitigation of overconsumption) is required. In other words, the key to overcome overconsumption is to turn to moderation, having in mind personal, societal and ecological well-being. By reviewing our values and goals, we will be able to change ineffective consumption patterns.

Mindfulness is proposed by Rosenberg (2004) as a way to help consumers realize the consequences of each consumption choice on consumers' health, society and nature. Moreover, it facilitates interpersonal relationships. Sheth et al. (2011) define mindful consumption as the moderation of the repetitive, excessive, and ambitious consumption which is achieved and enhanced by caring for the self, the society and the environment. Bahl et al (2016) have constructed a useful outline of the transformative potential of mindful consumption, which is based on the following factors, which can influence the transformation to mindful consumption choices, i.e. Attention, Acceptance, Awareness, Insight.

Intrinsic values and mindfulness

Closely related to the mindfulness and sustainable consumption, we can find in literature certain intrinsic values that relevant research indicates that are associated with these concepts. Based on empirical findings, some works claim that there exists a positive relationship between mindfulness and sustainable consumption behaviors as well as with intrinsic values (Subramaniam's, 2016; Subramaniam & Helm, 2019). Moreover, Subramaniam and Helm (2019) suggest that mindfulness is also positively related to Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE) and that PCE strengthens the positive relationship between mindfulness and sustainable consumption.

Intrinsic values are the beliefs we have about life, that guide our goals and behaviors and consequently influence the results of our choices. In the consumption context, customers' values have mainly to do with the critical evaluation of the advertising messages, and the criteria for selecting products and companies to buy from. Therefore, depending on the values that consumers have, their consumer behavior tends to be mindless or mindful. In other words, beliefs and values seem to explain mindful consumption-related behaviors (Nasr Bechwati et al., 2016).

Based on the above, it is evident that the domain of mindfulness is diverse and extended. It is not however, evident from field surveys whether some global patterns could be identified, or behavior is mostly influenced by external factors, such as advertisement. It is, on the other hand, of high importance to identify the various elements that could develop mindfulness, as this will motivate mindful and ecological consumption. This is the motivation of the present work, focusing on the association between mindfulness and values.

III. METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the work was to explore the relationship between mindfulness, sustainable consumption and specific values, which according to the literature seem to be related. Sustainable consumption behaviors were measured by the assessment of three related behaviors: environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, preference for companies with perceived Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), downshifting consumption. For the assessment of each of the above three categories (constructs), we used two to three questions which are items of original scales, widely used at academic research. Similarly, we assessed three categories of values (constructs): altruistic values, intrinsic values and perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE). This resulted to seven constructs in total.

The research focused on the Greek consumer community, and especially in adults who were expected to be aware of the mindfulness concepts. As the population for the survey, we considered people who were registered in a Greek mobile application mindfulness community, accounting to a total of more than thirty thousand active members. This approach was considered as they were considered to be closer to mindfulness, they would be more likely to they provide accurate, conscious answers, and more likely that they would understand the value and the purpose of the research.

A questionnaire was formulated, reflecting the constructs above and was sent by e-mail during the first quarter of 2022 to the members who had consented to receive e-mails. At the same time, the questionnaire was published on social networks. The survey remained active for one month and the e-mail was opened by 16,041 recipients. After the pre-processing phase and elimination of invalid values a total of 1,730 responses was used for analysis. The questionnaire was tested on four experts in order to check language clarity and determine the time it takes for an average individual to complete the questionnaire. Based on their feedback, the estimated time to complete it was about ten minutes and some wording changes took place.

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The scale items we measured were: mindfulness, altruism, intrinsic values, perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE), environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, preference for companies with perceived CSR and downshifting consumption. From the extended scales, we extracted a few indicative items (two to five items per scale) in order to be used in the survey. Since these scales are established measurement scales, widely used in literature of similar context and they have already been tested for reliability and validity in previous studies, we accepted that we can proceed with the analysis without the need to confirm reliability (Sousa et al. 2021). For the same reason, a formal pre-test was not carried out.

Frequencies, relative frequencies, mode and median were calculated for every question (item) and for the composite constructs, we calculated mean and we measured symmetry (Joshi et al., 2015). Descriptive statistics allowed us to take insights about the profile of Greek consumers who are willing to cultivate mindfulness.

In order to explore the relationship between the seven constructs we generated a correlation matrix. In addition to these constructs, we used two “broader constructs” that are the average of individual constructs. More specifically, we used:

1) Values [broader construct], which is the average of the three constructs that refer to values: a) altruism, b) intrinsic values, c) PCE constructs. It shows how much the respondent is characterized by all these values, as a whole.

2) Sustainable consumption behaviors (SC) [broader construct], which is the average of the three constructs that refer to sustainable consumption behaviors: a) environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, b) preference for companies with perceived CSR, c) downshifting consumption. It shows how much the respondent is characterized by all these sustainable behaviors, as a whole.

We added these broader constructs in order to explore how differently they correlate compared to the individual constructs of their category. For example, we wanted to explore how differently a) sustainable-consumption-behaviors-[broader construct] and b) downshifting-consumption (which is an individual construct of the sustainable-consumption-behaviors-[broader construct]) correlate with mindfulness construct. The reason for this is that, we aimed to include all the most indicative constructs in the survey, but at the same time we wanted to keep the questionnaire short. So, we used only two to five items of each original scale -while some original scales are considerably extended (e.g. the original FFMQ scale of mindfulness which contains 39 items). Thus, we expected relatively low correlations between the constructs. The broader-constructs, which combine all the individual constructs of the same category (and thus take into account more items) result into more comprehensive understanding of the correlations.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding the sample, 1,730 respondents are included and the following numbers provide demographic insights about the profile of Greek consumers who are willing to cultivate mindfulness (regardless of whether they are systematically practicing it or their current level of mindfulness). The key demographic deriving from the sample are the following:

- 82% of the respondents are women.
- 48% are of age between 36 and 50 and 27% are between 25 and 35 years old. That means that 75% of the respondents are between 25 and 50 years old.
- 50% are college graduates, while the rest of the sample almost divide between high school graduates and master / PhD holders.
- 76% have an annual income up to 20,000€ (divided almost equally into two income groups: Up to 10,000€ and 10,000€-20,000€).

For the analysis we use the following underlying variables (constructs): a) mindfulness, b) altruistic values, c) intrinsic values, d) Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE value), e) environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, f) preference for companies with perceived CSR, g) downshifting consumption behaviors. Those constructs were derived by grouping questionnaire items into seven constructs as follows:

1. Mindfulness (5 items)

2. Altruistic Values (3 items)
3. Intrinsic Values (3 items)
4. Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE value) (3 items)
5. Environmentally friendly consumption behaviors (3 items)
6. Preference for companies with perceived CSR (2 items)
7. Downshifting consumption (3 items)

All the questions in the questionnaire (apart from demographics) were measured at a 7-point Likert scale. For the underlying variables, the approach was to use the mean of each one showing the average of all the items that refer to each construct for all respondents. So, initially, we calculated the mean of the relevant items (of each construct) for each respondent and then the mean of the means of all respondents. Thus, the results for each underlying variable are enlightening regarding the level of a) mindfulness, b) altruistic values, c) intrinsic values, d) Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE value), e) environmentally friendly consumption behaviors, f) preference for companies with perceived CSR, g) downshifting consumption behaviors of our sample.

Some key results are the following:

- At a 7-point Likert scale:
 - o Mindfulness construct’s mean is equal to 4.16.
 - o The individual constructs’ mean that refer to the values examined are 5.94 (altruistic values), 4.80 (intrinsic values) and 5.26 (PCE value).
 - o The individual constructs’ mean that refer to the sustainable behaviors examined are 5.19 (environmentally friendly behaviors), 5.31 (preference for companies with perceived CSR) and 4.87 (downshifting consumption behaviors).
- All the constructs have a left – skewed distribution, except for mindfulness construct which tends to normal distribution.

Also, the correlation matrix for the constructs was produced as follows (figure 1).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Mindfulness	--								
2. Altruism	.173***	--							
3. Intrinsic Values	.442***	.103***	--						
4. PCE	.171***	.336***	.124***	--					
5. Values (broader construct)	.416***	.653***	.697***	.666***	--				
6. Environment	.268***	.366***	.148***	.297***	.382***	--			
7. CSR	.167***	.346***	.099***	.237***	.318***	.478***	--		
8. Downshifting	.284***	.259***	.097***	.206***	.264***	.484***	.387***	--	
9. SC (broader construct)	.301***	.407***	.144***	.310***	.404***	.822***	.780***	.784***	--

Note: *** $p < .001$, two-tailed. $N = 1370$.

Figure 1: Correlation matrix.

V. DISCUSSION

According to literature, there seems to be a positive relationship between mindfulness, sustainable consumption, and specific values. This assumption is indeed supported by the results of our research, at some extent. Our analysis indicated positive relationship between all these concepts. However, correlations were moderate or low. The strongest of the correlations was observed between mindfulness and intrinsic values ($r = .442$), meaning that people that hold

strong intrinsic values are more mindful. Following to this, altruistic values had moderate, positive correlation with environmentally friendly consumption behaviors ($r=.366$) and with preference for companies with perceived corporate social responsibility ($r=.346$). In other words, people that hold altruistic values have more environmentally friendly consumption behaviors and prefer to buy from companies that perform corporate social responsibility activities.

Similarly, we observe that:

- People that develop more sustainable consumption behaviors have stronger altruistic values ($r=.407$) and perceived consumer effectiveness (PCE) ($r=.310$).
- People who hold simultaneously altruistic and intrinsic values as well as perceived consumer effectiveness, prefer companies with CSR ($r=.318$) and adopt more environmentally friendly behaviors ($r=.382$) and general sustainable consumption behaviors ($r=.404$). The above results tend to confirm previous research regarding the relationship between mindfulness, sustainable consumption, and the relevant values.

Given that the sample used in the survey is familiar with the concept of mindfulness, we can gain an insight into the typical profile (based on modal characteristics) of Greek consumers interested in mindfulness. Based on the results, this typical profile of the Greek consumer who is willing to cultivate mindfulness could be described as: a college graduate woman, between 25-50 years old, with an annual income up to 20,000€. She is used to following sustainable consumptions behaviors, she has very strong altruistic values and strong intrinsic values, while she is also characterized by intense perceived consumer effectiveness. Finally, her behavior towards mindfulness is rather neutral, despite her willingness to cultivate it. Furthermore, we observed that Greek consumers who are familiar with the concept of mindfulness have very strong altruistic values and strong intrinsic values. They are, also, characterized by intense perceived consumer effectiveness (which defines whether a person believes they can change something in the world by changing their own consumption behavior). Moreover, they are used to following sustainable consumptions behaviors such as environmentally friendly and downshifting consumption behaviors while they also prefer companies with perceived corporate social responsibility.

As this work has to do with mindful consumption, these insights into consumer profile are useful for both research and marketers. The above findings are useful for marketers, as they may be the basis for the creation of a marketing persona which will facilitate market segmentation and targeting (Revella, 2015). Moreover, it will help marketers focus their marketing efforts on creating value for customers and satisfy their needs through the appropriate offerings (products, services, experiences) (Armstrong et al., 2017).

To sum up, we infer that the majority of the individuals that are willing to cultivate mindfulness have not yet achieved the desired levels of mindfulness and they are conscious about not being mindful at the time being. This suggests that there is a broad need for enhancing mindfulness which is mostly realized by young and middle-aged women.

VI. CONCLUSION

The work provided some useful insights and contributes at the existing body of research in the domain, but is not without limitations, which can be addressed in subsequent studies. This research was oriented towards people who are consciously concerned about the concept of mindfulness and are interested in practicing it. However, this does not ensure that respondents engage in the practice of mindfulness systematically and does not take into account how long and how often participants practice. Also, at the questionnaire, we included only a few items per construct in order to measure each behavior / attitude, due to two reasons: a) we tried the questionnaires to be easy and fast to complete and to have a high response rate, b) we aimed at including all the indicative and critical constructs of the concepts we explored. Future research could include more items for deeper study and more established results about correlations. Finally, it would be interesting in future to have results from research in different countries regarding the demographic profile of consumers who are familiar with the concept of mindfulness as well as their level of mindfulness, their attitude towards sustainable consumption and the relevant values that the current study discussed.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kabat-Zinn J. & Williams J., Mindfulness: diverse perspectives on its meaning, origins, and multiple applications at the intersection of science and dharma. *Contemporary Buddhism*, 12(1):1-18, 2011.
- [2] Confino, J., Google's head of mindfulness: 'goodness is good for business'. The guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/sustainable-business/google-meditation-mindfulness-technology>, 2014.
- [3] Bahl, S., Milne, G.R., Ross, S.M., Mick, D.G., Grier, S.A., Chugani, S.K., Chan, S., Gould, S.J., Cho, Y.-N., Dorsey, J.D., Schindler, R.M., Murdock, M.R., Mariani, S.B., Mindfulness. The Transformative Potential for Consumer, Societal, and Environmental Well-Being. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 35 (2): 198-210, 2016.
- [4] Sheth, J.N., Sethia, N.K. & Srinivas S., *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 39 (1): 21-39, 2011.

- [5] TechCrunch, Meditation and mindfulness apps continue their surge amid pandemic, <https://techcrunch.com/2020/05/28/meditation-and-mindfulness-apps-continue-their-surge-amid-pandemic/>, Last accessed: 20 May 2022
- [6] Bodhi, B., *A comprehensive manual of Abhidhamma*. WA: BPS Pariyatti Editions, 2000.
- [7] Brown, K. W., Ryan, R. M., & Creswell, J. D., Mindfulness: Theoretical Foundations and Evidence for its Salutary Effects. *Psychological Inquiry*, 18(4), 211–237, 2017
- [8] Stanszus, L., Education for sustainable consumption through mindfulness training: conceptualization and results of an intervention study. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability* 2017.
- [9] Rosenberg, E., Mindfulness and consumerism. American Psychological Association, 2004
- [10] Hayes S., Luoma J., Bond F., Masuda A, Lillis J., Acceptance and Commitment Therapy: Model, processes and outcomes, *Psychology Faculty Publications*. 101, 2006.
- [11] Kabat-Zinn, J., Mindfulness-based interventions in context: Past, present, and future. *Clinical Psychology: Science and Practice*, 10(2): 144–156, 2003
- [12] Kabat-Zinn, J., An outpatient program in behavioral medicine for chronic pain patients based on the practice of mindfulness meditation: Theoretical considerations and preliminary results. *General Hospital Psychiatry*, 4: 33–47., 1982.
- [13] Langer, E. J., & Moldoveanu, M., The Construct of Mindfulness. *Journal of Social Issues*. Vol. 56 (1): 1–9, 2000.
- [14] Mogilner, C., Kamvar, S. D., & Aaker, J., The shifting meaning of happiness. *Social Psychological & Personality Science*, 2(4), 395–402, 2011.
- [15] Shook, N.J., Ford, C., Strough, J., Delaney, R., Barker, D., In the Moment and Feeling Good: Age Differences in Mindfulness and Positive Affect. *American Psychological Association*, 3(4): 338–347, 2017.
- [16] Alispahic, S., Hasanbegovic-Anic, E., Mindfulness: Age and Gender Differences on a Bosnian Sample. *Psychological Thought*. 10(1):155–166, 2017.
- [17] Langer, E. J., & Moldoveanu, M., The Construct of Mindfulness. *Journal of Social Issues*. Vol. 56 (1): 1–9, 2000.
- [18] Pollock, C. L., Smith, S. D., Knowles, E. S., & Bruce, H. J., Mindfulness Limits Compliance with the That's-Not-AU Technique. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 24(11): 1153–1157, 1998
- [19] Sheth, J.N., Sethia, N.K. & Srinivas S., *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 39 (1): 21–39, 2011.
- [20] Rosenberg, E., *Mindfulness and consumerism*. American Psychological Association, 2004.
- [21] Bahl, S., Milne, G.R., Ross, S.M., Mick, D.G., Grier, S.A., Chugani, S.K., Chan, S., Gould, S.J., Cho, Y.-N., Dorsey, J.D., Schindler, R.M., Murdock, M.R., Mariani, S.B., Mindfulness. The Transformative Potential for Consumer, Societal, and Environmental Well-Being. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 35 (2): 198–210, 2016.
- [22] Subramaniam, B., Living in Present to Nurture the Future : Investigating the Association Between Mindfulness and Sustainable Consumption Behaviors Using Individuals ' Cognitive Personality , Values and Beliefs Variables, 2016.
- [23] Subramaniam, B., Helm, S., Exploring socio-cognitive mindfulness in the context of sustainable consumption. *Sustainability*. 11 (13), 2019.
- [24] Nasr Bechwati, N., Mounkkaddem Baalbaki, A., Nasr, N. & Baalbaki, I., Mindful Consumer Behavior: a Cross-Cultural Comparison. 3(10): 100–113, 2016.
- [25] Sousa, G.M., Lima-Araújo, G.L., Araújo, D.B., Brief mindfulness-based training and mindfulness trait attenuate psychological stress in university students: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Psychology* 9 (21), 2021.
- [26] Revella, A., Buyer Personas: How to gain insight into your customer's expectations - Align your marketing strategies and win more business. Wiley, 2015.
- [27] Armstrong, G., Kotler, P., Opresnik, M. O. , Marketing: An introduction. Global Edition, 2017.